

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING AND SIMULATION OF A SOFT ARRAY OF DIELECTRIC ELASTOMER ACTUATORS

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ABSTRACT

Dielectric elastomers (DEs) consist of thin membranes of dielectric material (e.g., silicone) coated with compliant electrodes. When subject to a high voltage, a DE undergoes an in-plane expansion which can be used for actuation purposes. Nowadays, most of the applications of DE actuators (DEAs) are based on single-degree-of-freedom systems. If many DEA elements are combined together in an array-like structure, a new generation of distributed and cooperative micro-actuators can be developed, with potential applications in fields such as soft robotics, distributed acoustics, and wearables. In this work, we present the first steps towards the development of such types of cooperative DEA systems. In particular, we report a finite element (FE) simulation study conducted on a one-dimensional array of silicone-based DEAs. Individual activation of each actuator in the array can be performed in an independent way, thus allowing to implement cooperative control paradigms. First, a FE model of the system is implemented in COMSOL environment and validated by means of experimental data. Then, a simulation analysis is conducted with the aim of understanding how the system parameters (e.g., geometry, pre-stress, actuators spacing) affect the overall electro-mechanical performance. The presented analysis will serve as a reference for the development of distributed cooperative DEA systems.

Keywords: Dielectric elastomer, dielectric elastomer actuators, array actuator, cooperative actuators, FE model, coupling effects

1. INTRODUCTION

Dielectric elastomers (DEs) represent a class of transducers capable of producing a mechanical deformation in response to a voltage signal. An intuitive explanation of the DE actuation

mechanism has been provided by Perline et al. [1]: it is based on the concept of Maxwell stress, i.e., the attractive force between the electrodes of a charged planar capacitor, which pushes them closer towards each other and leads to an expansion in their surface. Features of DE actuators (DEAs) include large deformations (up to at least 100%), high compliance, low power consumption, high energy density, and self-sensing [2]. Examples of applications of DEAs range from conventional valves and pumps [3] to more advanced systems such as soft robots [4], [5], loudspeakers [6], [7], artificial muscles [8], and Braille displays [9].

In recent years, several small-scale applications of DEAs have also started to emerge. Examples of fields that could benefit from the advantages of DE technology include micro-pumps [10], micro-robots [11], [12], micro-air vehicles [13], micro-underwater vehicles [14], and smart skins embedding tactile displays [15]. Up to date, most of these DEA applications rely on single degree-of-freedom systems, in which only one active element is used in a stand-alone configuration. In contrast, if many DEA elements are integrated in an array-like configuration and operated in a synergistic fashion, a cooperative system can be obtained. By combining the intrinsic compliance, energy efficiency, and self-sensing features of DEAs with cooperative control paradigms, a new generation of distributed micro-actuators can be developed, with potential applications in fields such as soft robotics, distributed acoustics, wearables, and wave generators, to mention a few. Naturally, the high complexity of cooperative DEA systems makes their design a highly challenging task, due to the strongly nonlinear response of the DE material, in conjunction with the coupled electro-mechanical effects which arise when many active transducers are packed together in a small space. In this perspective, numerical simulation tools can provide an effective means to support the

design, e.g., in terms of geometry, layout, and number of active DE elements which are involved in the process. It is remarked how the finite element (FE) method can be used to perform accurate structural simulations, and to provide detailed information on how different elements of an array interact with each other [16], [17]. In addition to that, a FE model can also be used as a distributed-parameter reference to verify the accuracy of reduced order models, e.g., lumped-parameter dynamic models to be used for feedback control purposes [6], [18].

As a first step towards the development of cooperative DEA systems, in this work we present a FE simulation study conducted on a one-dimensional array of DEA elements. The main goal is to understand how the available design parameters affect the spatially coupled electro-mechanical performance of the system. First, experimental characterization data collected on a DEA array prototype are used to calibrate and validate a COMSOL model of the device. Then, a simulation study is conducted with the aim of understanding how the free design parameters (electrodes geometry, electrode spacing, pre-stretch) affect the actuation behavior of the system. In particular, our primary interest is the systematic understanding of how the electro-mechanical interactions among neighbor actuators are affected by the design parameters. Such interactions might be either unwanted or desirable, depending on the amount of cooperation required in the target application, therefore understanding how we can properly control them, leveraging on the design, is key. The obtained results will serve as a starting point for the future development of high-performance DEA microarrays.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The realistic experimental setup is mentioned in Section 2, followed by the FE modeling, parameter calibration, and validation of the DE array are described in Section 3. In section 4, the simulation study is conducted. Finally, concluding remarks and future research directions are discussed in Section 5.

2. PHYSICAL DEA ARRAY

We consider DE arrays with the general layout shown in Fig FIGURE 1(a) (top view) and (b) (3D rendering). The array consists of a rectangular DE membrane, with the perimeter fixed on a rigid frame, and a set of active DEA units (three black areas in the example in the figure). The active units are obtained by applying circular electrode patches on the two faces of the DE membrane. The units are independent and can be actuated separately through the application of high voltage.

An experimental prototype based on this architecture has been presented in our earlier research work (FIGURE 1(c)), and is used as a base-reference for some of the analyses presented in this paper. The experimental prototype consists of a 50 μm -thick silicone membrane (Wacker Elastosil 2030 [20]) and carbon-based screen-printed electrodes. The array elements have same size and are uniformly spaced. In particular, the diameter of the electrode equals $D = 20$ mm, while the distance between two electrodes is chosen as $d = 15$ mm.

FIGURE 1: LAYOUT OF THE DEA ARRAY CONCEPT STUDIED IN THIS PAPER. (A) TOP VIEW, (B) 3D RENDERING (CREATED IN COMSOL), AND (C) EXPERIMENTAL PROTOTYPE.

The latter value also coincides with the distance between the electrodes and the external rigid frame. For additional details on the experimental setup, please refer to [19].

The presented layout has been chosen as a simple, yet representative proof-of-concept of a DEA array, through which we can determine the feasibility and accuracy of the FE modeling approach. Besides, it also permits us to study the electro-mechanical coupling that occurs among the different DE elements. It is worthwhile mentioning that this geometry can be combined with elastic biasing structures, similarly to what is commonly done in single-degree-of-freedom DEAs [21], thus allowing to exploit it for actuation purposes.

3. MODEL CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION

A crucial aspect of cooperative DEA system is the quantification of the electro-mechanical interactions existing among the spatially distributed elements of the array. Such interactions can occur, e.g., when the application of voltage to a single DEA causes the mechanical force-strain characteristic of the neighboring DE membrane to change, even if the latter has not been actuated. To properly investigate this phenomenon, a FE model is first developed in this section. Then, based on experiments conducted on the prototype in FIGURE 1(c), the developed model is calibrated and validated.

FIGURE 2: RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTAL CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION OF THE DEA ARRAY MODEL. THE CONTINUOUS CURVES REPRESENT THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS, WHILE THE OTHERS REPRESENT THE SIMULATED RESULTS. THE 3D SKETCHES PROVIDE INFORMATION ON WHICH MEMBRANE IS ELECTRICALLY ACTUATED (IN RED) IN THE CORRESPONDING CONFIGURATIONS. ONLY THE EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENTS REPORTED IN THE FIRST SUBPLOT ON THE UPPER LEFT-HAND SIDE (DEFAULT AND CONF.1) ARE USED FOR MODEL CALIBRATION. THE REMAINING ONES, INSTEAD, ARE USED FOR THE VALIDATION PROCESS.

3.1 FE model description

For our modeling study, we consider the 1-by-3 DEA array in FIGURE 1. A three-dimensional FE model of the structure is implemented in COMSOL, as shown in FIGURE 1(a) and (b). Here, the active DE area covered by the electrode is depicted in black, the passive silicone is represented in brown, and the external rigid frame used to clamp the silicone is reported in grey. To reflect the behavior of the experimental setup, the deformation and voltage are chosen as control parameters in the FE simulations, by applying a prescribed displacement along the z-axis on the circular surface sketched in red (see FIGURE 1(b)). This circular area has a radius $r = 2.5\text{mm}$, i.e., the same size as a rigid intender which, in the experimental setup, is used for measurement purposes, driven by a linear motor which deforms the membrane out-of-plane. The measured output of each experiment is represented by the z-axis force component measured on the same surface. To prevent electromechanical instabilities a small (5%) uniaxial pre-stretch is applied along the x-axis of the membrane. The motion of the membrane perimeter along the y- and z-axes is prohibited by setting the displacement equal to zero at the edges.

An incompressible Yeoh free-energy function is chosen for both the DE and the passive silicone (with same material parameters for both), in order to model the large-strain mechanical response of the elastomer [22]. Electro-mechanical coupling is modeled by adding an electrostatic potential

contribution into the elastic energy of each individual actuator unit, similarly to [17].

	Configurations						
	Default	1	2	3	4	5	6
First actuator	OFF	ON	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON	ON
Second actuator	OFF	OFF	ON	OFF	ON	OFF	ON
Third actuator	OFF	OFF	OFF	ON	ON	ON	OFF

Table 1: Voltage configurations used for experimental characterization and model simulations.

The mechanical (ψ_m) and electrical (ψ_{el}) free-energy density contributions of the DE are reported in the following:

$$\psi_m = \sum_{i=1}^3 c_{i0} \left(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2 - 3 \right)^i + p(J-1), \quad (1)$$

$$\psi_{el} = -0.5\epsilon_0\epsilon_r J E^T C^{-1} E, \quad (2)$$

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ represent the principal stretches, while ϵ_0 and ϵ_r denote the vacuum and DE relative permittivity, respectively. The remaining parameters are defined as follows:

- E is the nominal electric field vector, computed as the negated gradient of the electric voltage in the undeformed configuration;
- $J = \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3$ is the volume ratio;
- C is the Elastic Cauchy-Green tensor in the local coordinate system;
- p is a Lagrange multiplier which accounts for the material incompressibility constraint.

3.2 Characterization experiments

To calibrate and validate the model, the same experiments described in [19] are used. They are performed by deforming out-of-plane the first DEA on the left of FIGURE 1(c) with a linear motor, while the output force is recorded using a load cell. This type of test is repeated several times, by considering different combinations of DEAs which are simultaneously activated via high voltage. Table 1 shows which actuator is activated in each case, for all of the considered tests.

Each subplot presented in FIGURE 2 **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the mechanical characteristics (blue and red curves) of the first measured actuator, with voltage equal to 0 kV (default configuration) and 2.5 kV applied to the active DEs in each configuration (configuration i , $i = 1, \dots, 6$). The sketches shown in the bottom-right part in each subplot illustrate the specific conditions under which the test is conducted. In each configuration, the force is measured on the indentation surface of the deformed DE, and the DE membranes on which high voltage is applied are depicted in red.

3.3 Model Identification and Validation

In order to ensure that the presented model accurately reflects the behavior of the realized prototype, a calibration of the free material parameters in (1)-(2) is performed a-priori, based on the collected experimental data. The known parameters are the geometrical dimensions, as well as the silicone permittivity, which is $\epsilon_r = 2.8$ for the given material [20]. The only unknown material parameters are the free coefficients of the hyperelastic Yeoh model, denoted as c_{10} , c_{20} , c_{30} (cf. (1)).

Parameters calibration is performed using the Optimization Module in COMSOL. The curves present in the first subplot on the upper left part of FIGURE 2 **Error! Reference source not found.** (Default + Conf. 1) are used for calibration, and yield the following values for the three Yeoh parameters: $c_{10} = 0.19$ MPa, $c_{20} = 0.025$ MPa, $c_{30} = -2.84$ kPa. The results of the model are reported as dashed lines in FIGURE 2 **Error! Reference source not found.**. All the remaining experiments, i.e., Conf. 2-6, are used as validation sets. From FIGURE 2 **Error! Reference source not found.**, it is clear how the FE model accurately describes the experimental setup in each one of the considered configurations. A further observation concerns the small mutual influence among the different DEA neighbor membranes. In fact, the gap among the curves in the default configuration is remarkably smaller compared to configurations 2, 3, and 4. As a final remark, note how the model only captures the average trend of each experimental curve, but not the rate-dependent viscoelastic hysteresis. Since in this work we intend to focus on

FIGURE 3: SKETCH OF A 1-BY-2 ARRAY OF THE DEAS FE MODEL USED FOR THE SIMULATION STUDY, PRESENTED IN TOP-VIEW (A) AND 3D (B). THE INVESTIGATED GEOMETRIC PARAMETERS ARE MARKED IN THE TEXT AREAS.

	00	01	10	11
First actuator	OFF	OFF	ON	ON
Second actuator	OFF	ON	OFF	ON

Table 2: Voltage configurations used for the simulation study.

identifying the average trend of the characteristic curves, a stationary model is used for all of the different loading scenarios. Therefore, the model explicitly ignores the rate-dependent hysteresis present in the experimental curves, which is due to the material losses.

4. MODEL-BASED PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS

When a DE membrane is electrically actuated via high voltage, the neighboring DEA may undergo a change in its mechanical response. To understand how the free geometrical parameters affect the interaction between different DEA membranes, a parametric study is presented in this section.

4.1 Array with a single mechanically-biased element

Based on the model described in Section 3, a case study is defined for the parameter study. To simplify the analysis, a system consisting of a 1-by-2 array of DEAs is considered in this section. This allows understanding how a variation of the geometrical parameters affects the interaction between two individual DEA membranes, by keeping the numerical complexity of the model as low as possible.

In the array structure considered in FIGURE 3, the input out-of-plane deformation and the resulting output force measurements are performed on the second DE membrane, through the application of the same boundary conditions as in Section 3. Details on which actuator is electrically actuated in the various configurations are reported in Table 2. In order to quantify the existing electro-mechanical coupling, we define an actuation force of the second DE unit as follows. Given the same amount of deflection, the actuation force is given by the difference between the force in configurations 00 and 10. The ratio of the actuation force in configuration 10 and that in configuration 01 allows us to quantify the coupling in relative

terms. For an easier understanding, only the peak value obtained for the maximum applied deflection 10 mm is computed.

The list of nominal geometric parameters for the studied configuration is as follows:

- Total array length = 20 cm,
- DE membrane diameter = 20 mm,
- Distance of the electrode from the external rigid frame along the y-axis = 15 mm.

The simulation study is conducted by keeping all the parameters constant at their nominal values, while changing only one of them at the time. The geometric parameters studied with their respective ranges of set values are discussed in the following:

- DE membrane spacing: [1, 11, 21] mm. This parameter is highly relevant for the design, because the smaller the relative distance among the electrodes, the greater the actuation density of the system as well as the expected electro-mechanical coupling. On the other hand, placing them too close together could produce undesirable effects, i.e., the creation of an electric arc through air due to high voltage. To account for this technical limitation, the minimum admissible value is determined based on the dielectric strength of the air (3 kV/mm) [23]. Besides, the maximum value chosen for the parameter range corresponds to the distance that makes the interaction between the membranes practically inexistent. The results of this investigation are shown in FIGURE 4.
- Pre-stretch in-plane: [5, 10, 20] % of the total array length. The pre-stretch is considered unidirectional and is applied along the x-axis. This parameter is studied to understand whether or not the increase of the pre-stretch has an effect on the electro-mechanical coupling between the neighboring elements. The results of this investigation are shown in FIGURE 5.
- Unstretched array thickness: [10, 20, 30, 40, 50] μm . Investigation of this parameter is also highly important, since the reduction in thickness also implies a smaller voltage required to produce a same electric field (and, in turn, achieve the same Maxwell stress). The set of voltages which allow keeping the same nominal electric field for the different thickness values is as follows: [0.6, 1.2, 1.8, 2.4, 3] kV. On the one hand, a smaller voltage gives the possibility of placing the actuators closer to each other, and thus we expect a higher potential electro-mechanical interaction. On the other hand, reducing the thickness also has the effect of reducing the absolute force of the system. The results of this investigation are shown in FIGURE 6.

By analyzing the simulation results, we can confirm that an out-of-plane deformed DE membrane undergoes changes in the force-deformation characteristic curve when the adjacent actuator is electrically activated. The simulations show that, from the actuation force perspective, such effects can be increased by moving the actuators closer to each other, by increasing the unidirectional pre-stretch and the thickness of the array structure. So that, the optimum is reached by setting 1 mm

as electrode spacing, pre-stretch equal to 20% of the total array length and structure thickness equal to 50 μm .

Placing the electrodes as close as possible permits the DE membrane to benefit from the expansion of the area of its neighbor, to which voltage has been applied. As a consequence, the DE membrane varies its characteristic curve compared to the 00 configuration, as it requires a lower force to reach the same displacement. This explanation, combined with the previous description, also explains the increase in electro-mechanical coupling in the case of varying array thickness. Increasing the unidirectional pre-stretch, instead, decreases the membrane thickness. Given the same applied voltage, the Maxwell becomes larger, and thus the gap between configuration 00 and configurations 10 or 01 is increased. Nevertheless, observing the relative measurements we can remark that the maximum interaction is reached by reducing the distance between the membranes (1 mm), their thickness (10 μm), and the applied pre-stretch (5% of the total array length). In this case, the actuation force value in configuration 10 is 18.5% of those in configuration 01. In comparison, the relative actuation force value achieved in the previous optimal case is 14%.

4.2 Array with multiple mechanically-biased elements

In the previous section, the behavior of the overall membrane is analyzed. In order to exploit each element of the DE array as an actuator system, a mechanical bias needs to be provided to each element [21]. An interesting aspect to analyze concerns the behavior of the array when both DE membranes are deformed with the same biasing system, and then actuated with different voltage values. Therefore, a new case study is realized based on the first most favorable combination of parameters for electro-mechanical coupling, i.e. electrodes placed at the minimum allowed distance from each other, pre-stretch equal to 20% of the total array length, and structure thickness equal to 50 μm . A 3D rendering sketch of the biased actuator is shown in FIGURE 7 **Error! Reference source not found.**

Two different types of biasing configurations are considered for this study, i.e., constant force and constant displacement. In the former case, the displacement changes when the membranes are electrically actuated, while in the latter it is the force that varies upon activation. By comparing these two different and extreme types of biasing mechanisms, we can verify which one provides a higher electro-mechanical coupling between two neighboring elements. Note that biasing systems used in common practice generally exhibit an intermediate behavior among those two. To provide comparable results, the constant biasing force and displacement chosen for the two studies are such that they correspond to the same starting equilibrium configuration with no applied voltage, i.e., a force of 0.12 N and a displacement of 5 mm. In addition, relative measurements are computed in order to describe how much the output force/displacement increases/decreases compared to the case in which only the second membrane is electrically active.

The results are shown in FIGURE 8 and FIGURE 9, for the constant force and constant displacement biasing, respectively. In each plot, the red curve is obtained by actuating the single

FIGURE 4: INTERACTION AMONG THE ACTUATORS AS THE SPACING IS VARIED.

FIGURE 5: INTERACTION AMONG THE ACTUATORS AS THE UNIDIRECTIONAL PRE-STRETCH VARIES.

FIGURE 6: INTERACTION AMONG THE ACTUATORS AS THE ARRAY UNSTRETCHED THICKNESS VARIES.

FIGURE 7: 3D RENDERING SKETCH OF A 1-BY-2 ARRAY IN A BIASED CONFIGURATION.

FIGURE 8: (A) RESULTS OBTAINED BY SETTING THE FORCE TO A CONSTANT VALUE OF 0.12 N FOR BOTH DE MEMBRANES (CONSTANT FORCE BIAS), AND MEASURING THE DISPLACEMENT OF THE SECOND ACTUATOR. THE CONFIGURATIONS SHOWN IN DIFFERENT COLORS ARE DEFINED IN Table 2. (B) RELATIVE DISPLACEMENT MEASUREMENTS RESULTS.

FIGURE 9: (A) RESULTS OBTAINED BY SETTING THE DISPLACEMENT TO A CONSTANT VALUE OF 5 MM FOR BOTH DE MEMBRANES (CONSTANT-DISPLACEMENT BIAS), AND MEASURING THE RESULTING FORCE FROM THE SECOND ACTUATOR. THE CONFIGURATIONS SHOWN IN DIFFERENT COLORS ARE EXPLAINED IN Table 2. (B) RELATIVE FORCE MEASUREMENTS RESULTS.

measured actuator, while the yellow one is obtained by driving both actuators with high voltage. Note how, in the latter case, a larger gap can be seen in the case with constant force bias. In fact, focusing on the results obtained for an applied voltage of 3 kV, the force value reached in configuration 10 is only 16% greater than in configuration 01, while the same quantity becomes 44% greater by imposing a constant displacement.

These results clearly show that mutual electro-mechanical interactions exist among the different actuators, which can be properly triggered by tuning the driving strategy accordingly. If a constant displacement bias is prescribed, instead, the activation of the neighboring DE has only a small influence, since the deformation along the z-axis is completely locked. Therefore, implementing a constant force biasing mechanism will make the influences existing between different DE membranes more observable, compared to a constant displacement one. In reality, this can be practically implemented via either a hanging mass or a soft and long spring element.

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, a FE model for a 1-by-3 array of DEAs has been implemented, identified, and validated. Subsequently, a parametric study has been performed to understand how geometric variations of the proposed structure can increase the interaction among different DEA units. The electro-mechanical interaction is studied by analyzing the changes in the force-deformation characteristic of a DEA element caused by the electrical activation of different combinations of neighbors. It is observed how, from the actuation force point of view, the interaction can be increased by arranging the actuators at the minimum possible distance from each other, increasing the pre-stretch, and the membrane thickness. Furthermore, two simple cooperative DEA systems are considered, in which the single units operate under constant force and biasing displacement, respectively. FE simulation studies have revealed that the constant force bias makes the interactions existing between different DE membranes more visible.

It should be noted that, in the presented case study, the minimum distance at which the electrodes can be placed depends on the air dielectric strength. Possible future applications may involve placing the DEAs array in a fluid with high dielectric strength, so that the electrodes can be placed even closer to each other and thus increase their influence. Other future developments include the realization of a miniaturized DEAs array structure that, combined with the studies performed in this work and an appropriate control algorithm, will allow us to develop the first prototype of a small-scale collaborative system. Finally, the electro-mechanical coupling effects will also be studied in a sensing setting, in order to include distributed self-sensing features into the cooperative DEAs.

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